

TYCHO Astrometry — Error Propagation

L Lindegren (1982 Nov 22)

Lund Observatory
Box 1107
S-22104 LUND, Sweden

1. General Case

Let ϵ_i be the timing accuracy for a single transit across a group of (4 or 8) slits inclined by the angle i with respect to the transverse direction (viz., $i = 0$ for "vertical" slits, $\pm 45^\circ$ for chevron slits). With $v = 180$ as/s, the mean error of the longitudinal field coordinate at the observed time of transit is $v\epsilon_i$ (neglecting geometrical calibration errors). The corresponding error in the coordinate perpendicular to the slits is $v\epsilon_i \cos i$.

To get the corresponding error on the sky, we have to add the attitude error in the direction perpendicular to the slits. If σ_L , σ_T denote the a posteriori attitude mean errors in the longitudinal and transverse direction, respectively, the attitude mean error in direction i is $(\sigma_L^2 \cos^2 i + \sigma_T^2 \sin^2 i)^{1/2}$. Thus, the mean error on the sky of the star's coordinate in that direction is

$$\sigma_i = [(v^2 \epsilon_i^2 + \sigma_L^2) \cos^2 i + \sigma_T^2 \sin^2 i]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

The mean errors of the two-dimensional position (λ, β) after completed mission are

$$\sigma_\lambda = C_{i\lambda} \sigma_i, \quad \sigma_\beta = C_{i\beta} \sigma_i \quad (2)$$

$C_{i\lambda}$, $C_{i\beta}$ are coefficients of improvement analogous to those of the main mission (C_1, C_3). (N.B.: σ_λ is a true arc, and so contains implicitly the factor $\cos \beta$.)

2. Case of Vertical Slits Only

In the original TYCHO proposal, the astrometry was supposed to be derived mainly from the vertical SM segment, in much the same way as Step 3 of the main mission. In this case ($i = 0$), assuming that the longitudinal attitude is accurately obtained from the set solutions ($\sigma_L \approx 0$), eqn (1) reduces to

$$\sigma_0 = v\epsilon_0 \quad (3)$$

Since the observation geometry is exactly the same as for the main mission, C_0 are obtained simply by scaling C_1, C_3 according to the effective number of observations. This should take three factors into account: (i) that the vertical slits have a different height ($h_0 =$ transverse FOV) than the main mission ($H = 54$ am); (ii) that there are two SM crossings per great circle scan (p and f), but only one abscissa measurement; and (iii) that the total dead time ($f = 0.18$) is not included in C_1, C_3 , but could be included in C_i for simplicity. With $h_0 = 40$ am we get

$$C_{0\lambda} = [2(1-f)(h_0/H)]^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_1 \approx 0.177 \quad (4a)$$

$$C_{0\beta} = [2(1-f)(h_0/H)]^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_3 \approx 0.143 \quad (4b)$$

(using $C_1 = 0.195, C_3 = 0.157$, MAT-HIP-3137, p. 6).

3. Case of Chevron Slits Only

With no vertical slits, the transverse attitude uncertainty becomes important. For $i = \pm 45^\circ$, and neglecting σ_L , eqn (1) is

$$\sigma_{45} = [\frac{1}{2}(v^2 \epsilon_{45}^2 + \sigma_T^2)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

The observing geometry is also different from that with vertical slits. For the same transverse FOV ($h_{45} = h_0$, where h_{45} includes both segments of the chevron) the total number of observations is however the same; they are only more favourably distributed in position angle. Even at the ecliptic we get an almost isotropic distribution of the effective scanning directions (i.e. perpendicular to the slits). Thus we expect

$$C_{45\lambda} \approx C_{45\beta} \approx \frac{1}{2}(C_{0\lambda} + C_{0\beta}) \approx 0.160 \quad (6)$$

4. Numerical Comparison

The performance goal of Jan 8th, 1982: "0.1 as for the longitudinal field coordinate" (at $B = 10$), was written with the vertical slits in mind and must be interpreted as $v\epsilon_0 \leq 0.1$ as. Thus, from (1) we have $\sigma_0 \leq 0.1$ as and from (4), $\sigma_\lambda \leq 0.018$ as, $\sigma_\beta \leq 0.014$ as. Put $\sigma_* \equiv \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_\lambda + \sigma_\beta) \leq 0.016$ as.

In the case of chevron slits only, we can start with the performance goal $\sigma_* \leq 0.016$ as and work backwards. With (6) we get $\sigma_{45} \leq 0.1$ as. If $\sigma_T = 0.1$ as (ITT 6.1.2.6.2), this gives in turn $v\epsilon_{45} \leq 0.1$ as.

5. Conclusions

- (i) Since the coefficients of improvement C_i are (on the average) the same for vertical and chevron slits (of the same transverse height), the astrometric performance of the SM can be judged simply from the ~~sky coordinate error perpendicular to the slits for a single transit,~~ σ_i in (1).
- (ii) With $\sigma_T = 0.1$ as, the requirements $v\sigma_0 \leq 0.1$ as and $v\sigma_{45} \leq 0.1$ as are equivalent, viz. $\sigma_i \leq 0.1$ as.
- (iii) The above requirements correspond to the final astrometric accuracy $\sigma_* \leq 0.016$ as. They could possibly be somewhat relaxed, since the number given in the TYCHO proposal (Høg et al., Strasbourg Colloquium, February 1982) is $\sigma_* = 0.03$ as at $B = 10$.